

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D4.2 – New digital, molecular, chemical/physical data archive for biological and paleobiological materials

v1.0

Deliverables information

Work package	WP4
Deliverable leader	UNIBO
Author(s)	Romandini, Matteo (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2271-9991): DBC - UNIBO, Ravenna Bernardini, Sara (https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7283-6323): DBC - UNIBO, Ravenna Vergara, Alessandro (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4135-0245): UNINA Birolo, Leila (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0915-7501): UNINA Pollio, Antonino (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3018-7921): UNINA Sannino, Maria Francesca (https://orcid.org/0009-0001-1488-2521): UNINA Pizzimenti, Silvia (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6230-5681): UNINA Rook, Lorenzo (https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8923-5428): UNIFI-DST Peri, Emanuele (https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8635-5379): UNIFI-DST
Deliverable status	Final
Deliverable version	V1.0
Date	22 December 2025

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

CHANGES

CULTURAL HERITAGE ACTIVE INNOVATION FOR NEX-GEN SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY
EXTENDED PARTNERSHIP

Deliverable history

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Institution(s)
V0.1	November 22 nd , 2025	adding text sections and contributions	All partners
V1.0	December 22 st , 2025	final version of common text, contributions homogenization and refinement	UNIBO

Spoke Information

Scientific coordinator(s)

Paolo Francesco Romano – francescopaolo.romano@cnr.it

Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale – Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

Via Biblioteca 4 - c/o Palazzo Ingrassia, 95124 Catania (CT), Italia

Scientific co-coordinator(s)

Monica Galeotti – monica.galeotti@cultura.gov.it

Opificio delle Pietre Dure

Fortezza da Basso, Viale Strozzi 1, 50129 Firenze, Italia

Spoke Partners

No.	Name of Partner	Acronym	Role
1	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CNR	Spoke leader
2	Opificio delle Pietre Dure	OPD	Spoke co-leader
3	Sapienza Università di Roma	UNIRM1	Member
4	Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	UNINA	Member
5	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	UNIBO	Member
6	Università degli Studi di Catania	UNICT	Member
7	Università degli Studi di Firenze (DST, BIO)	UNIFI	Member
8	Gran Sasso Science Institute	GSSI	Member
9	EDIL CO. S.r.l.	EdilCo	Member

Executive Summary

This report is part of the work performed in the project PNRR PE 5 "CHANGES", and specifically in Spoke 5 "Science and Technologies for Sustainable Diagnostics for Cultural Heritage", WP4 "Advanced diagnostics and scientific methods for organic material"

It presents and discusses the results obtained in the project, planned as: **R4.2 Development and implementation of non-invasive taphonomy based methods as well as chemical/physical and molecular approaches to assess diagenetic processes in organic materials** and constitutes one of the Deliverables produced: *D4.2 - New digital, molecular, chemical/physical data archive for biological and paleobiological materials*.

The scope of this report is to present and discuss the activities performed in WP4 by the research partners involved.

UNIBO contributed to the creation of a new digital archive of isotopic data through extensive $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ analyses on human, animal, and modern plant samples from diverse archaeological contexts. The work focused on reconstructing mobility, provenance, and landscape use by developing reliable local baselines and regional isoscapes, especially in areas with limited existing data. Samples were processed using standardized chemical protocols and MC-ICPMS measurements, and results were integrated with archaeological and environmental information. Modern plant sampling across South America, Italy, the Middle East, and the Arabian Peninsula further supported new isotope development. The datasets will provide a lasting resource for future research in archaeology, ecology, and conservation science.

UNINA has shown that complementary chromatographic and mass-spectrometric techniques provide a robust framework for reliably identifying archaeological organic residues and deepening interpretations of ancient practices. A minimally invasive MALDI-MSI workflow using trypsin-functionalized sheets shows strong potential for spatially resolved protein analysis in cultural-heritage materials, though sensitivity and peptide localization remain key challenges.

In addition, the experiments conducted by **UNINA** on light and relative humidity have provided deeper insight into the influence of environmental parameters on the growth and metabolic behavior of fungal species frequently associated with the deterioration of paper-based materials. The species-specific responses observed under different experimental conditions made it possible to identify factors that either promote or limit microbial colonization. These findings contribute to defining more accurate risk scenarios and support the development of preventive strategies for the conservation of documentary heritage.

UNIFI (DST) highlights that advanced analytical tools based on non-invasive techniques (CT-scan; Surface scan) implemented by powerful methodologies of elaboration/visualization in virtual environments strengthen our knowledge and visualization of "deep time" palaeobiological record, offering deeper insights into new digital and physical data archive

for deep time paleobiological materials (e.g. retrodeformation, biomechanics, and much more). The potential of non-invasive approaches and analytical methods is crucial when dealing with such rare and unique cultural heritage objects.

The totality of the experiences here reported contributes to the need of supporting the knowledge consolidation process with digital instruments and scientific methods, leading to the common goal of a better diagnostic investigation of biological and palaeobiological material.

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

CHANGE^S

CULTURAL HERITAGE ACTIVE INNOVATION FOR NEXT-GEN SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY
EXTENDED PARTNERSHIP

Table of contents

1. Introduction	8
2.1 UNIBO: Strontium isotope analysis in archaeology and new baseline development for mobility studies.....	9
2.1.1 Introduction	9
2.1.2 Methodology	10
2.1.3 Main outcome and conclusions	12
2.2 UNINA: The challenge of organic residue analysis in archaeology and a novel approach for minimally invasive protein sampling for mass spectrometry imaging	13
2.2.1 Introduction.....	13
2.2.2 Results.....	14
2.2.3 Methodology	18
2.2.4 Conclusions	20
2.3 UNINA: Characterizing potential biodeteriogenic fungi from heritage contexts: experimental evaluations for sustainable conservation.....	22
2.3.1 Introduction.....	22
2.3.2 Results.....	22
2.3.3 Methodology	28
2.3.4 Conclusions	29
2.4 UNIFI (DST): Diagnostics and applications on paleobiological materials from deep time chronologies.....	30
2.4.1 Introduction	30
2.4.2 Methodology	31
2.4.3 Results and Conclusions	35
3. Conclusions.....	39
References	40

1. Introduction

Strontium isotope analysis ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) is a key tool for investigating human and animal mobility, provenance, and patterns of landscape use in archaeological, ecological and forensic research. Since strontium transfers from bedrock to organisms without significant fractionation, its isotopic signature reliably reflects local geological backgrounds. However, the interpretation of isotopic data is often limited by the availability of robust baselines and by the geological heterogeneity of many regions. Existing isoscapes (isotopic distribution maps) to use as referential material remain incomplete or missing in several areas of the world, constraining the reconstruction of mobility patterns. Archaeological contexts also frequently lack well-preserved or sufficient materials suitable for baseline construction, increasing the need for modern environmental proxies such as plants and soils. Recent research therefore relies more frequently on multi-proxy approaches to strengthen provenance studies and expand regional isotopic datasets. UNIBO applied strontium isotope analysis to a wide range of archaeological materials, complemented by the analysis of modern plants to reinforce local baselines and support more robust mobility reconstructions. Prioritising the analysis of modern plants allows to preserve archaeological materials and to overcome the absence of suitable samples.

Organic residue analysis from archaeological ceramics, when combined with vessel morphology, offers valuable insights into ancient dietary habits, cultural practices, and technological traditions. However, challenges such as scarce residues, contamination risks, and low biomarker specificity demand carefully designed analytical strategies. To address these issues, UNINA organize a workflow integrating lipid and sugar analysis with shotgun and targeted proteomics enhancing the reliability of vessel-use interpretation. In parallel, protein identification in artworks has traditionally relied on invasive micro-sampling for bottom-up proteomic analysis, and despite advances in trace detection, these methods remain inherently invasive. A minimally invasive trypsin-functionalized sheet enables on-surface protein digestion and, for the first time, MALDI-MSI imaging of protein distribution in artworks, advancing non-destructive cultural heritage analysis.

The biodeterioration of paper-based materials represents a significant concern for the preservation of cultural heritage, as paper—mainly composed of cellulose and other polysaccharides—serves as an easily degradable substrate for numerous microorganisms [DBP22]. Among these, filamentous fungi are considered the most damaging agents: through the production of extracellular enzymes (e.g., cellulases and hemicellulases), they can hydrolyze cellulose fibers, causing loss of cohesion, fragility, pigmented spots, and chromatic alterations [SCM14]. The establishment of fungal contamination is closely linked to microclimatic conditions, particularly relative humidity, temperature, and substrate composition, as well as the presence of organic additives such as adhesives [BM19]. Numerous studies have shown that genera such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Cladosporium*, and *Chaetomium* are among the most frequently isolated from books, documents, and manuscripts preserved in archives and libraries [PSM19]. Understanding the growth mechanisms and degradation processes of these microorganisms, as

the UNINA team did, is essential for developing more effective prevention and intervention strategies, thereby reducing the risk of irreversible damage to paper artifacts.

Developing new diagnostic and applications for the study of palaeobiological materials from deep time chronologies to investigate evolutionary patterns, functional morphology and other palaeoecological traits in fossil animals is crucial because of the unique nature of the fossil record (definitely included by UNESCO 1970 Convention under the definition of “cultural heritage”). The UNIFI(DST) unit developed a set of non-invasive procedures and advanced analytical tools for diagnostics, and reconstruction of information useful for the conservation, enhancement and study of palaeobiological materials (namely retrodeformation procedures, and palaeobiological reconstruction for biomechanic inferences).

2.1 UNIBO: Strontium isotope analysis in archaeology and new baseline development for mobility studies

2.1.1 Introduction

UNIBO involvement in WP4 concerning the creation of a new digital, molecular, chemical/physical data archive for biological and palaeobiological materials regarded the application of strontium isotope ratio analysis on a wide range of archaeological material to investigate migratory patterns and landscape use by humans and animals. The analysis of the strontium isotope ratio $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ allows us to trace the geological area of growth and/or exploitation of the analysed sample (for a review see [B06]. The isotopic ratio is linked to the geological formation and relatively influenced by environmental factors (e.g. proximity to the sea). Strontium isotopes cycle from bedrock to soil and then to the consumers without measurable fractionation [HQB04]. Any $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ fractionation is analytically corrected during MS measurement by normalisation to a conventional value [EGD01]. The joint analysis of materials that provide a local reference - known as the baseline - is essential. To this end, we analyse animals and plants from the area where the archaeological remains were found and its surroundings, to gain insight into the mobility patterns of the analysed human groups and the movements of animals. These proxies provide a good representation of the area in which they grew: plants consistently reflect the average of the bioavailable strontium ratio in a given geological background, and this averaging effect increases along the food chain [BPM99]. Therefore, when including animal samples as a baseline their isotope ratio will represent the average of the strontium ratio of the feeding area. An accurate sample selection is therefore crucial, considering modern plants growing in places far from anthropized areas, and animals from archaeological contexts (to avoid present-day pollutants as food with non-local origin) with low mobility and a narrow feeding range (e.g. pig). When analysing human and animal, dental enamel is sampled: its mineralised structure is less affected by diagenesis and allow to preserve the biogenic strontium value; moreover, teeth have a known formation time and do not remodel,

providing the information about that specific time interval [N12]. In some cases, bones are analysed as part of the baseline, as their porous structure makes them more affected to diagenesis and consequently their strontium ratio tends to reflect that of the surrounding soil [PBB02].

Hence, depending on the area under investigation, geological heterogeneity can affect the interpretation of isotopic data from human archaeological samples, making the availability of local baselines essential. For this reason, geographic maps of isotopic value distribution (isoscares) are increasingly used in archaeological research, however, for many regions they are still limited or entirely lacking (see [BCW20]; [LCB22]). Archaeological contexts do not always provide all the necessary proxies or well-preserved materials suitable for isotopic analysis. Human remains could be scattered and fragmented, preventing a direct reconstruction of the whole skeleton; animal remains may be incomplete, residue of a single event, or not locally raised, thus complicating contextual interpretation. Moreover, material can be scarce or poorly preserved, making it difficult to establish a robust baseline and resulting in partial isotopic analyses and interpretations.

For this reason, within WP4 UNIBO also carried out an extensive strontium isotope ratio analysis on modern plants to collect data contributing to local and regional isoscape development. This approach supports the identification of individual provenance even when other proxies are missing. Importantly, it also enables reconstruction of contextual dynamics while preserving archaeological material. The UNIBO work therefore focused primarily on human, animal, and modern plant remains from contexts investigated by the Laboratory of Osteoarchaeology and Paleoanthropology (Bones Lab) of the Department of Cultural Heritage. The analysed materials came from sites differing in both chronology and geographical location (e.g., Italy, South America, Middle East) and were part of the laboratory's various research projects.

2.1.2 Methodology

The material analysed included mostly human teeth from South America (Brazil and Argentina), Italy, Uzbekistan, the Emirates, and Oman. Sampling was minimally invasive and conducted by collecting approximately 5-10 mg of dental enamel with a Dremel® drill (Fig. 1b). When available, animal remains (teeth and bones) from the same archaeological contexts were also analysed to serve as baselines. Modern plant remains were likewise examined for almost all contexts (South America, the Emirates, and Oman). The samples from Italy were integrated with previously published data from the Italian isoscape [LCB22], but where possible, new data were also generated. The availability of modern plant samples depended on the possibility for the team to carry out fieldwork and to survey and collect material over a sufficiently representative area (multiple samples within a radius of approx. 1 km from the site, avoiding cultivated areas, settlements, and roads). Each sample consisted of leaves and branches from different modern plants, combined to obtain a more representative average value for each location. In dedicated areas (i.e., South America and Oman), modern plant sampling also followed the distribution of different geological formations over larger areas, contributing to the creation of an isoscape. For Oman, where the group has ongoing projects, soil samples were additionally analysed due to the scarcity of isotopic data for the region. For the same reason, a database

covering the rest of the Arabian Peninsula and part of Asia was compiled to address specific archaeological questions and to compensate for the lack of isotopic information.

Preparation, treatment, chemical protocol and MC-ICPMS measurements for strontium analysis. Plant samples are cleaned with MilliQ water to remove dust, soil and other possible contaminants. Samples are then dried in an oven (up to 650 °C) and subsequently weighed (approx. 5-10 mg) and dissolved in 3M HNO₃ for the chemical treatment required for strontium extraction in a clean room (Fig. 1a). Bone and tooth samples are directly dissolved in 3M HNO₃. The chemical protocol consists of loading the dissolved samples in Teflon columns previously filled with Eichrom Sr-spec resin (Eichrom Technologies, LLC) [HCD92] for extraction chromatography. Elements other than Sr are removed by three sequential washes with 3M HNO₃, after which strontium is eluted with MilliQ water [ALC21]. The obtained solution is then measured by a multi-collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (MC-ICPMS, ThermoFisher Scientific, Neptune™) (Fig. 1). The chemical protocol was carried out at the Department of Chemical and Geological Sciences of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, while the measurement of the isotopic composition of the samples at the Centro Interdipartimentale Grandi Strumenti (CIGS, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia). During each analytical session, repeated strontium measurements of the reference material NIST SRM 987 were performed, ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr values of the samples are then normalized to the accepted value for NIST SRM 987 of 0.710248 [MHB01]. Data correction was performed using the SrDr Excel software by [LWG20]. The analyses were conducted on a total of 326 samples.

Figure 1: schematic workflow of the preparation, chemical protocol, and MS measurements for strontium analysis, with details of modern plant sample preparation (a) and dental enamel processing (b).

2.1.3 Main outcome and conclusions

The results of the strontium isotope ratio measurements were integrated with the archaeological, anthropological and ecological data available -either collected by the group or retrieved from the literature- for the reconstruction of mobility patterns in each context. These data have contributed to PhD theses, excavation reports, and research missions that form part of the national and international collaborations of the Laboratory of Osteoarchaeology and Paleoanthropology (Bones Lab) of the Department of Cultural Heritage of UNIBO. As the group is involved in multiple ongoing projects, most of the datasets are currently in preparation for publication (e.g., Italian and South American archaeological contexts), others are part of missions still in progress (Oman), while some have already been submitted or published ([SGL25] – Regional isoscape of South America) in collaboration with colleagues from the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (Fig. 2).

Once published the data generated are fully compliant with the FAIR principles, guaranteeing their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. These results, in fact, will help expand regional strontium datasets, facilitating future research in these areas. Since strontium values are linked to the geological background and only minimally influenced by external factors, the collection of such extensive datasets - and their dissemination through international, multidisciplinary scientific publications - will support the development of new studies and reinforce ongoing research within the scientific community, not only in archaeology but also in ecology and conservation science.

Figure 2: spatial distribution of strontium isotopes in the Paraná Delta (Argentina, Uruguay) and surrounding areas. Isoscape model (a) and associated spatial uncertainty map (b) (from [SGL25]).

Participation to conference:

Sara Bernardini, Stefano Magri, Antonino Vazzana, Stefano Benazzi, Matteo Romandini, "Written in the teeth: a multi analytical approach to reconstruct life history and mobility through high-resolution microscopy and mass spectrometry of archaeological dental tissues" at the workshop *Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage: Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5*, held in Catania from 28th to 30th October 2025.

2.2 UNINA: The challenge of organic residue analysis in archaeology and a novel approach for minimally invasive protein sampling for mass spectrometry imaging

2.2.1 Introduction

By examining the residues preserved within archaeological ceramics, we can gain valuable insights into the original functions of these vessels and the foods that past communities prepared or consumed [DCBE20]. When this biochemical evidence is integrated with information on vessel morphology and intended use, it provides a rich perspective on daily life, including diet, cultural practices, craft traditions, trade networks, and broader patterns of societal development.

However, our analytical work faces several key challenges. These include: the limited quantity and heterogeneous distribution of surviving residues; the risk of environmental contamination and alterations arising from ageing processes and microbial activity, and the low specificity of biomarkers such as fatty acids and sugars, which complicates the accurate identification of their sources.

Taken together, these factors highlight the complexity of analysing ancient or degraded materials and the need for carefully tailored methodological approaches.

Our workflow is designed to address these challenges through a sequence of complementary steps. First, we cluster and contextualise samples in collaboration with archaeologists, considering vessel shape and potential function, as these characteristics often indicate how a container was used and what it may have held. We then conduct analyses of lipids, sugars, and other small organic molecules to obtain an initial chemical profile of the contents. This is followed by shotgun proteomic analysis of selected samples, allowing a more detailed exploration of preserved proteins. Finally, we apply targeted proteomics to refine our understanding of vessel use, with particular attention to the detection of species-specific peptides.

Protein identification in works of art traditionally requires invasive micro-sampling, followed by protein digestion and analysis using bottom-up proteomics. While advanced mass spectrometric based techniques can now detect trace substances, these methods remain invasive.

Recently, we developed a novel minimally invasive method for the analysis of proteinaceous materials in works of art [CNRMGB18]. This approach involves the use of a trypsin-functionalized

cellulose acetate sheet, which digests proteins in situ on the surface of a work of art without any removal of material from the artifact. After just 10 min of contact at room temperature (RT), this bioactive film generates and extracts sufficient peptides for unambiguous identification of the protein binder by proteomic analysis.

A major advancement of this technique is its potential for spatially resolved imaging of surfaces or cross-sections of works of art. This study proposes the first use of MALDI-MSI on a trypsin-functionalized sheet, reflecting the protein content distribution of the work of art with which it has been in contact.

2.2.2 Results

Characterization of organic residues from archeological sites by means of advanced chromatographic and mass spectrometry-based techniques

The characterization of the organic residue analysis of findings from the Pani Loriga site in Sardinia, Italy and from Herculaneum, Campania, Italy have been carried out using various sample pretreatments and advanced chromatographic and mass spectrometric techniques. Lipids, sugars, and proteins have been characterized. Protein analysis remains challenging due to preservation issues, contamination, and extraction complexity, targeted methods like multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) has been applied here for the first time in order to improve the identification.

Case study 1: Archaeological potteries from Pani Loriga – Sardinia (end of 7th century BC)

The archaeological site of Pani Loriga, near modern Santadi in southwestern Sardinia, was founded in the late 7th century BC as part of the Phoenician colony of Sulky's strategy to control routes between the coast and the resource-rich interior. Its importance continued into the Punic period. Recent excavations have revealed extensive 6th–5th century BC structures on the eastern slope of the hill, indicating a large, organized settlement beneath an acropolis. The western slope contained Phoenician-Punic necropolises, while a sacred area, later used in the Roman period, stood at the eastern edge.

During excavation campaigns, archaeologists collected a diverse set of samples from vessels recovered. The study applied a multi-step analytical workflow combining gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS), shotgun proteomics, and targeted proteomics (LC-MS/MS in MRM mode) to investigate the organic residues preserved in these ceramic artifacts. The central challenge addressed by the researchers was the difficulty of reliably identifying organic archaeological residues, particularly proteins, which degrade over time and are frequently subject to contamination. To confront this, they first classified vessels by morphology and hypothesized functional role, assuming that vessel shape correlates with typical use and therefore with the types of residues likely to be found.

GC-MS served as an initial clustering tool for lipids, sugars, and small organic compounds. Although molecular profiles were limited, similarly shaped vessels showed similar compositions. Saturated and unsaturated fatty acids, palmitic (C16:0), stearic (C18:0), and oleic (C18:1), were common, indicating degraded triglyceride-based fats of animal or plant origin; glycerol was also frequent. Diterpenes from pine pitch, likely used as waterproofing, is identified in amphorae,

plates, pitchers, and pots but not in basins or cups, suggesting selective sealing practices. One amphora (Am1) contained azelaic acid, evidence of oxidized unsaturated fats. Sugars occurred in most samples, pointing to residues from plant foods, cereals, legumes, fruits, or vegetables, and suggesting broad use of vessels for processing plant materials.

Table 1: Major compounds identified by GC-MS analyses in all the samples. Different colours refer to different class of compounds, arbitrarily divided in carboxylic acids (light yellow), fatty acids (yellow), sugars (blue), terpenoids (green) and alcohols (red). Abbreviations: for fatty acids Cx:y, x: number of carbon atoms, y: number of unsaturation, for dicarboxylic acids diCx, x: number of carbon atoms.

class	molecule	Pot		Pitcher					Cup	Basin		Lamp	Plate	Amphora									
		Po1	Po2	PI1	PI2	PI3	PI4	PI5	Cu1	Ba1	Ba2	La1	Pl1	Am1	Am2	Am3	Am4	Am5	Am6	Am7	Am8	Am9	
carboxylic acids																							
	acetic acid																						
	dic9																						
fatty acids																							
	C14																						
	C15																						
	C16																						
	C18																						
	C18:1																						
	C20																						
	monopalmitin																						
sugars																							
	arabinose																						
	galactose																						
	xylose																						
	glucose																						
	mannose																						
	ramnose																						
	inositol																						
terpenoids																							
	dehydroabietic acid																						
	methyl dehydroabietate																						
	7-oxodehydroabietic acid																						
	retene																						
alchols																							
	glycerol																						

Given the complexity and degradation of ancient proteins, multiple extraction and digestion protocols were applied. Shotgun proteomics proved challenging due to protein binding to ceramic matrices, rapid degradation, and extremely low concentrations, though trace proteins were detected in a few samples. Serum albumin occurred frequently—including in controls—and was treated as probable contamination. More informative were peptides from haemoglobin and caseins in vessels associated with food preparation.

A key case was a cooking tray (Ct2) with scorched surfaces: burnt areas produced no data, but

unburnt areas yielded haemoglobin α/β and α -S1-casein peptides. Targeted LC-MS/MS (MRM) confirmed multiple milk proteins, α -S1, α -S2, κ -caseins, α -lactalbumin, and β -lactoglobulin, matching bovine milk, with minor indications of sheep milk. Haemoglobin persisted, indicating use for both dairy and meat preparations.

A pitcher (Pi1) showed a similar protein profile, suggesting multifunctional food processing. These findings fit with an agro-pastoral economy reliant on cattle, small livestock, and diverse culinary practices.

A small plate containing a bone fragment provided another critical case. While morphology could not identify the bone, proteomics revealed type I collagen suitable for taxonomic assignment. BLASTp comparisons indicated *Sus scrofa* (wild boar or domestic pig), and high peptide deamidation supported authenticity and excluded modern contamination.

Overall, the study demonstrates the value of an integrated analytical approach. GC-MS offers chemical fingerprints but limited taxonomic resolution; shotgun proteomics adds biological information despite degradation; and targeted proteomics—applied here for the first time in archaeological residue analysis—resolves ambiguous identifications via species-specific marker peptides. Correlating these datasets with vessel morphology and archaeological context enabled a coherent interpretation of vessel function at Pani Loriga.

Case study 2: Carbonised residues from the archaeological site of Herculaneum – Campania (79 AD).

As a preliminary investigation, carbonised residues from the archaeological site of Herculaneum were analysed by GC-MS using a combined procedure that enables the identification of both sugars and lipids from the same micro-sample. We report initial results from two items: a possible carbonized bread and a possible glass jar (Figure 3). The carbonized bread shows the presence of galactose and glucose, likely derived from cereal-based materials. Differently, the glass jar also contains fructose, suggesting a sweet liquid. In addition, molecular markers of pine pitch were detected in the lipid fraction (data not shown), supporting the hypothesis that the jar was used as a liquid container.

Figure 3: GC-MS chromatogram of the sugar fraction of the carbonised bread and the glass jar.

An innovative minimally invasive method for mass spectrometry imaging of protein content in cultural heritage objects.

To address the need for minimally invasive sampling, a non-invasive method based on immobilized trypsin reported in-situ digestion of protein has been optimized. This sampling method has been coupled with MALDI mass spectrometry imaging in order to obtain a spatial resolved protein analysis of surface. This study proposes the first use of MALDI-MSI on a trypsin-functionalized sheet, reflecting the protein content distribution of the work of art with which it has been in contact. Following in situ digestion, the sheet is mounted on a glass slide and analyzed by an AP-MALDI source coupled to an Orbitrap Q-Exactive mass spectrometer, after matrix deposition. The MSI datasets are processed using a home-built database implemented on the Metaspaces annotation platform. Preliminary tests on casein containing samples suggest this integrated approach offers significant potential for future applications in cultural heritage studies (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the proposed approach combining minimally invasive sampling with MALDI-MSI for protein analysis of surfaces and cross-sections of works of art.

Approximately 40 peptides originating from casein glue were identified, with the most intense signals homogeneously distributed across the film surface (Figure 5). The results obtained from the experiment conducted directly on the trypsin-functionalized film confirmed that the sheet provided a relatively uniform peptide distribution across its surface.

Figure 5: Results obtained on the trypsin-functionalized sheet after contact with the casein glue replica for 10 min at

room temperature (RT). The square image shows the highly homogeneous spatial distribution of the peptide signal at m/z 1267.7 across the film.

The moistening required for trypsin digestion, as well as the subsequent matrix application, did not produce any macroscopic alteration in peptide localization. However, when the same experiment was performed on a sample consisting of two distinct layers (casein glue and lysozyme), the spatial localization of peptides was visibly lost. This observation highlights the need to test and implement new strategies to minimize wetting prior to sampling and to reduce film movement during the sampling process.

2.2.3 Methodology

Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS)

Lipid and sugar analyses were performed using adapted established GC-MS protocols, as described in reference [MDNBTCBLFAC20].

Protein Digestion

Multiple extraction and digestion protocols were tested for analyzing protein residues absorbed in pottery. All workflows included protein extraction, enzymatic hydrolysis, and MS/database analysis for protein identification. For bone samples, digestion followed the method in reference [VDCPNB16], involving EDTA pretreatment and incubation in 6 M urea without cysteine reduction or alkylation.

In all cases, the resulting tryptic peptides were desalted and concentrated on C18 Stage-Tips, dried, resuspended in 2% ACN/0.5% formic acid, and analyzed by MALDI-MS using a CHCA matrix.

Untargeted LC-MS/MS

Peptide mixtures were analyzed by positive-ion full scan and data-dependent MS on a Q-Exactive Orbitrap coupled to a nanoUHPLC system. Separation was performed on a PepMap column with a 3–70% ACN gradient over 60 minutes at 300 nL/min, and spectra were collected across m/z 375–1500.

Alternatively, bone fragments were analyzed on an Agilent Q-ToF system with a chip-based setup. Samples were enriched on a 40 nL column and separated on a C18 capillary column using a 3–80% ACN gradient. Data-dependent MS/MS targeted the three most abundant ions per scan, prioritizing doubly and triply charged ions.

Data were converted to MGF format and searched with MASCOT against the SwissProt database (Chordata taxonomy). Search parameters included trypsin digestion, up to three missed cleavages, 10 ppm precursor tolerance, 0.6 Da fragment tolerance, and variable modifications such as methionine oxidation, Asn/Gln deamidation, and collagen-related hydroxylation. LC-MS/MS datasets are deposited in Mendeley Data.

Targeted LC-MS/MS

Peptide mixtures were analyzed using an MRM method on a triple-quadrupole mass spectrometer with nano-HPLC. Separation used a BEH C18 column with an ACN/formic acid gradient from 7% to 95% buffer B, followed by re-equilibration. MS settings included 3900 V spray voltage, 150 °C interface temperature, specific gas and nebulizer conditions, and acquisition at 5 points per peak with 3 ms dwell time. Precursor/product ions in the 300–1000 m/z range.

Preparation of the trypsin-functionalized sheets

Trypsin functionalized sheets for protein analysis were prepared as previously detailed in [CNRMGB18, NKSCSCB21]. However, slight changes have been introduced to adapt the sheets to the MSI set-up. Briefly:

A sheet of cellulose acetate was cut under hood obtaining 1x1 cm pieces.

25 µL of 0.1 mg/mL of Vmh2 hydrophobin (2.5 µg) in 60% ethanol solution was spotted on the surfaces and incubated at 60 °C until the complete evaporation of the solution.

The pieces were washed with 50 µL of 60% ethanol solution to remove the excess of protein and dried at 60 °C.

This procedure was repeated twice before proceeding with the enzyme immobilization. The total amount of Vmh2 hydrophobin added was 5 µg.

A volume of 25 µL of 1 µg/µL of trypsin solution (25 µg) in 50 mM of ammonium bicarbonate at pH 7.0 (AMBIC) were added on the coated surfaces for 5 min at room temperature (RT).

After the incubation, the surfaces were washed with 50 µL of 50 mM of AMBIC to remove the excess of trypsin and they were left to dry at RT.

Before use, a solution of AMBIC was sprayed on the functionalized surfaces to moisten the surface and restore the optimal working environment of the trypsin (or 25 µL of AMBIC were added on top).

Sampling and preparation of the glass slide for MALDI-MSI

For in situ hydrolysis of the paint mock-up, a small area of the sample was placed in direct contact with the trypsin-functionalized surface for 10 min at RT. After contact, the sheet was removed and allowed to dry. Once dried, it was mounted on a glass slide with the surface that had been in contact with the sample facing upward. A 5 mg/mL CHCA matrix solution was then applied by spraying, using an automatic sprayer (Shimadzu) allowing multiple deposition cycles (17 layers in total). MALDI-MSI measurements were subsequently performed directly on the treated sheet.

MALDI-imaging acquisition

MALDI-MSI measurements were performed on an Atmospheric Pressure MALDI (TransMIT, Germany) source able to reach a pixel size of 5 µm and coupled to an Orbitrap Q-Exactive mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) at a mass resolution of 70,000. Samples were analysed in positive mode over a mass range of about 500–5000 m/z, depending on the experiment. Acquisition was performed using full pixel mode at 25 µm spatial resolution. Spectra were generally averaged prior to analysis.

MSI data analysis

The MSI datasets were annotated through the METASPACE 2020 platform using a custom peptide database generated from UniProt entries corresponding to the main protein sequences typically found in pictorial binders.

In addition, manual inspection of the MSI datasets was performed using FreeStyle software. Peptide identification was achieved by direct matching against an in-house peptide database constructed from experimental LC–MS/MS data acquired on the same casein–pigment paint reconstruction analyzed in this study. This database also includes modified peptides that are not present in the database implemented in METASPACE 2020.

2.2.4 Conclusions

Characterization of organic residues from archeological sites by means of advanced chromatographic and mass spectrometry-based techniques

The investigation of organic residues of archaeological findings demonstrates that a combination of complementary analytical techniques is essential for improving the reliability of organic residue identification. The study provides insights into ancient dietary practices, food preparation activities, and material technology. The implemented methodology based establishes a robust framework that can be applied to future archaeometric research aiming to bridge biomolecular evidence with archaeological interpretation.

An innovative minimally invasive method for mass spectrometry imaging of protein content in cultural heritage objects

The aim of this study was to assess the feasibility of a novel analytical approach that combines minimally invasive sampling with MALDI-MSI for the analysis of cultural heritage (CH) materials. Specifically, we developed a strategy that integrates trypsin-functionalized sheets for on-sample enzymatic digestion with subsequent MALDI-MSI analysis performed directly on the sheet, thereby capturing the spatial distribution of proteins from the sample surface. This method is designed to deliver spatially resolved molecular information while minimizing the impact on original artworks.

Experiments conducted on casein-based paint replicas provided key insights into both the potential and challenges of this approach. Several factors—such as low peptide recovery, matrix-related spectral interferences, and uneven peptide distribution—were found to significantly affect the sensitivity and reproducibility of MSI measurements.

Experiments employing an automatic sprayer for CHCA matrix deposition yielded improved results, achieving more homogeneous peptide distribution and enhanced peptide detection. Approximately 40 casein-derived peptides were reproducibly identified and spatially localized across the film surface. Future optimization of matrix deposition parameters (e.g., number of layers, solvent composition, and drying conditions) will be critical to maximize peptide ionization efficiency while minimizing background interference.

Despite these promising results, several challenges remain. MALDI-MSI analysis on functionalized

sheets exposed to multiple protein layers—such as casein combined with lysozyme—showed partial loss of spatial localization, suggesting peptide migration during sampling. This highlights the need for refined sampling protocols that can preserve spatial fidelity and minimize molecular diffusion.

Future work will focus on (1) refining sampling and digestion protocols to improve reproducibility and spatial resolution; (2) enhancing MALDI-MSI acquisition sensitivity through optimized matrix deposition and instrumental parameters; (3) developing advanced data interpretation tools that encompass modified peptide databases; (4) conducting validation studies on historical samples.

Contribution to congresses:

Silvia Pizzimenti, Brunella Cipolletta, Myriam Fiore, Miriam Alberico, Marco Morelli, Paola Giardina, Paola Cicatiello, Bertrand Thomas, Andrea Carpentieri, Caroline Tokarski, Gaetano Di Pasquale, Leila Birolo, Alessandro Vergara, *"The challenge of organic residue analysis in archaeology and a novel approach for minimally invasive protein sampling for mass spectrometry imaging."* Workshop *"Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage: Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5"*, held in Catania from 28 to 30 October 2025.

Brunella Cipolletta, Bertrand Thomas, Georgia Ntasi, Paola Cicatiello, Paola Giardina, Caroline Tokarski, and Leila Birolo, *"Immobilized trypsin – enhanced MALDI-Imaging analysis of surfaces and cross-sections of works of art"*, TECHNART 2025 - International Conference on Analytical Techniques for Heritage Studies and Conservation, Perugia, May 6-9, 2025.

2.3 UNINA: Characterizing potential biodeteriogenic fungi from heritage contexts: experimental evaluations for sustainable conservation.

2.3.1 Introduction

Paper-based cultural heritage materials are among the most vulnerable substrates to microbiological deterioration, particularly by filamentous fungi, whose enzymatic activity can cause structural weakening, chromatic alterations, and irreversible loss of information. Within this project, the work carried out by the Biology Laboratory of UniNA aimed to deepen the understanding of fungal diversity associated with archives and libraries, and to clarify the environmental factors that influence fungal growth and degradative potential. To this end, sampling campaigns were conducted in several historical archives and libraries, allowing the isolation and characterization of a large number of fungal strains. These isolates were identified using morphological and molecular approaches and incorporated into a dedicated reference collection (MYCUF), which now represents a stable resource for further studies. Building on this foundation, experimental activities were carried out to investigate how key microclimatic parameters—specifically light exposure and relative humidity—affect fungal colonization, metabolism, and degradative activity on different types of paper substrates. The goal of these studies was to generate experimental evidence to guide preventive conservation strategies and support the development of more effective environmental control measures for paper-based cultural heritage materials and the environments in which they are preserved.

2.3.2 Results

MYCUF collection

By investigating new archives and libraries, the mycological collection has been enriched with new entities, currently comprising a total of 94 strains [Tab. 2]. Each strain was identified using three molecular markers and characterized through assays for cellulolytic and proteolytic activity. Finally, all strains were cryopreserved at -80°C , lyophilized, and photographed to monitor their growth on different culture media, thereby assessing the macroscopic morphology of the mycelium and its pigmentation. This allowed me to evaluate the biodiversity of this small but peculiar flora, dominated by the phylum Ascomycota, with the family Aspergillaceae being the most represented and the genera *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, and *Cladosporium* the most prevalent.

Table 2: sequences accession numbers deposited at NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>).

YCUF_ID	ITS	Bt2a	CMD	YCUF_ID	ITS	Bt2a	CMD
001_f	load	load	-	038_f	PX502257.1	PX562627.1	PX562632.1
002_f	PX502529.1	PX562664.1	-	039_f	PX502260.1	PX562630.1	PX562635.1
003_f	load	load	-	040_f	PX502523.1	-	-
004_f	load	-	-	041_f	load	-	-
005_f	PX502528.1	-	-	042_f	PX503659.1	-	-
006_f	load	-	-	043_f	load	-	-
007_f	load	load	-	058_f	PX502530.1	PX562665.1	-
008_f	load	load	load	059_f	PX560368.1	PX562672.1	-
009_f	PX503658.1	PX562637.1	PX562649.1	060_f	PX560365.1	PX562669.1	PX562677.1
010_f	PX502527.1	PX562663.1	-	061_f	PX560369.1	PX562673.1	PX562679.1
011_f	PX502526.1	PX562662.1	PX562668.1	062_f	PX560371.1	PX562675.1	PX562681.1
012_f	load	load	load	063_f	PX560366.1	PX562670.1	PX562678.1
013_f	PX503657.1	PX562636.1	PX562648.1	064_f	PX560370.1	PX562674.1	PX562680.1
014_f	PX503660.1	PX562638.1	PX562650.1	065_f	PX560367.1	PX562671.1	-
015_f	PV199124.1	PV390663.1	PV390664.1	066_f	PX560372.1	PX562676.1	-
016_f	load	load	load	069_f	PX570233.1	PX646273	-
017_f	PX502258.1	PX562628.1	PX562633.1	070_f	PX570228.1	PX646269	-
018_f	PX502259.1	PX562629.1	PX562634.1	071_f	PX570225.1	-	PX646278
019_f	load	load	load	072_f	PX570226.1	PX646267	PX646279
020_f	load	load	load	073_f	PX570231.1	PX646271	PX646282
021_f	load	load	load	074_f	PX570238.1	PX646275	PX646285
022_f	PX502256.1	PX562626.1	PX562631.1	075_f	PX570230.1	PX646270	PX646281
023_f	PX503662.1	PX562640.1	PX562652.1	076_f	PX570237.1	PX646274	PX646284
024_f	PX503664.1	PX562642.1	PX562654.1	077_f	PX570232.1	PX646272	PX646283
025_f	PX503665.1	PX562643.1	PX562655.1	078_f	PX570240.1	PX646276	PX646287
026_f	PX503666.1	PX562644.1	PX562656.1	079_f	PX570227.1	PX646268	PX646280
027_f	PX503667.1	PX562645.1	PX562657.1	080_f	PX570239.1	-	PX646286
028_f	PX503669.1	PX562647.1	PX562658.1	081_f	PX570241.1	PX646277	PX646288
029_f	PX503663.1	PX562641.1	PX562653.1	082_f	PX570235.1	-	load
030_f	PX503670.1	-	PX562659.1	083_f	PX570229.1	-	-
031_f	PX502524.1	PX562660.1	PX562666.1	084_f	PX570234.1	-	-
032_f	PX502525.1	PX562661.1	PX562667.1	089_f	PX570236.1	-	-
033_f	load	load	load	090_f	PX685535	load	load
034_f	PX503668.1	PX562646.1	-	091_f	PX685536	load	load
035_f	load	load	load	092_f	PX685537	load	load
036_f	PX503661.1	PX562639.1	PX562651.1	093_f	PX685538	load	load
037_f	load	load	load				

Fungal growth on different papers

To evaluate how environmental parameters, namely light and relative humidity, influence fungal growth, I set up a preliminary experiment to assess the growth of three different species among those most frequently found during my sampling: *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Cladosporium cladosporioides* and *Aspergillus niger*. The fungi were tested on two different types of paper: pure cellulose (Whatman No. 1) and cotton-based (Amalfi paper), both in their normal form and artificially aged, for a total of four types of paper used. The experiment was carried out in darkness, over a total period of four weeks with weekly monitoring at a temperature of $\pm 25^{\circ}\text{C}$. This experimental set was used as a control for subsequent experiments.

Using a metallographic microscope, I measured the thickness of the mycelial growth on the four types of paper, selecting measurement points on the specimens including the central point, the median points, and the distal points. *P. chrysogenum* showed greater growth on normal Amalfi paper, followed by normal Whatman 1 paper. *C. cladosporioides* grew to a similar thickness on both these types of paper [Tab. 3]. I was also able to observe the growth pattern of the mycelium of these two species on these supports, which developed radially, starting from the center of the specimen and expanding outward. Conversely, *A. niger* grew more in thickness on aged Amalfi paper, showing a ring-shaped growth pattern, with greater development at the median points of the paper specimens [Tab. 4].

Through image analysis using FIJI software, I calculated the area colonized by the different mycelia. *P. chrysogenum* and *A. niger* colonized larger areas on normal Whatman 1 paper, whereas *C. cladosporioides* colonized more extensively on aged Amalfi paper.

Table 3: thickness growth of the mycelium of *P. chrysogenum*, *C. cladosporioides* and *A. niger* in the dark on Whatman 1 normal, Whatman 1 aged, Amalfi normal and Amalfi aged paper.

Table 4: area occupied by the mycelia of *P. chrysogenum*, *C. cladosporioides* and *A. niger* on the paper specimens, calculated using the FIJI software.

Fungal growth under different wavelengths

Although fungi are heterotrophic organisms, it is well established in the literature that light can influence their growth, sporulation and metabolite production. To evaluate the impact of exposure to monochromatic radiation and white light, I set up an experiment using pure cellulose samples, namely Whatman 1 paper, inoculated separately with spore suspensions of *Penicillium chrysogenum* and *Cladosporium cladosporioides*. I built boxes in which I placed the inoculated samples, each equipped with a different light source: one with cool white light at 6226 K, one with warm white light at 2435 K, one with monochromatic blue light peaking at 426 nm, and one with monochromatic red light peaking at 631 nm [Fig. 6 e Fig. 7].

Exposure to monochromatic light makes it possible to detect whether the fungus shows sensitivity to a specific wavelength. Exposure to white light, on the other hand, allows the assessment of whether the fungal response under monochromatic light is comparable to that observed under white light, whose emission spectrum is characterized by a concentration of energy at the same wavelength as the corresponding monochromatic source. Spectral irradiance measurements were taken at the bottom of the boxes to properly adjust the lighting conditions and ensure uniformity across the entire surface.

I evaluated the mycelial thickness under each lighting condition for both species and found that

light influenced fungal growth. Overall, compared to the control, the mycelia grew very little. The growth of *Penicillium chrysogenum* under cool white light was almost completely inhibited, while the thickness of *Cladosporium cladosporioides* was significantly reduced compared to the control. By analyzing the areas colonized by the mycelia with FIJI software, I observed that although the thickness of *P. chrysogenum* under blue light was very limited, the colonized area under this monochromatic source was nearly half that of the control [Tab. 5]. Conversely, the area colonized by *C. cladosporioides* under red and warm white light was much larger than in the control, suggesting that these two sources may have promoted mycelial growth [Tab. 6]. SEM imaging is currently in progress and will provide more detailed insights into the growth of these mycelia under the influence of these light sources.

Figure 6: the peak wavelength spectral irradiance for warm white light is equal to that recorded for the corresponding red monochromatic light.

Figure 7: the peak wavelength spectral irradiance for cool white light is equal to that recorded for the corresponding monochromatic blue light.

Table 5: mycelial thickness of *P. chrysogenum* and *C. cladosporioides* grown on plain Whatman 1 paper under different wavelengths (cool white, blue, warm white, and red).

Table 6: area occupied by the mycelia of *P. chrysogenum* and *C. cladosporioides* grown on plain Whatman 1 paper under different wavelengths (cool white, blue, warm white and red).

Fungal growth on different humidity ranges

Relative humidity is considered a key parameter in biodeterioration processes. High humidity levels create favorable conditions for spore germination and biofilm production, resulting in both aesthetic and structural damage to organic and inorganic materials. For this reason, the effect of different relative humidity conditions on two types of paper, normal and artificially aged Whatman 1, inoculated with *P. chrysogenum*, was investigated in order to better understand which ranges represent a greater risk for the preservation of paper artifacts. Following the setup of the previous experiments, boxes containing trays filled with saline solutions ($MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, K_2CO_3 , and $NaCl$) were used to recreate three relative humidity ranges (33% – 44%

– 75%), and the thickness of *P. chrysogenum* mycelium growing on the two paper types was evaluated.

At 33% relative humidity, I measured a very limited growth only at the end of the experiment, but the measurements were challenging since the paper curled on itself. At 44%, growth was observed only during the last week, and still much lower compared to the control. At 75% relative humidity, growth occurred but appeared to be reduced compared to the control. Further analysis of the acquired images will provide more detailed information regarding the areas colonized by the mycelia.

2.3.3 Methodology

Mycological collection

Samples were collected from books and documents using sterile swabs in areas showing visible signs of contamination. They were then transferred onto various selective fungal culture media (PDA, MALT, YES, CYA, CD) to facilitate the isolation of a broad range of filamentous fungi. Preliminary morphological identification was carried out through microscopic observation using specific stains (Lactophenol Blue and Calcofluor). For all isolates, a standardized DNA extraction (CTAB method) and PCR protocol was performed, targeting the molecular markers ITS, β -tubulin, and calmodulin, using primers reported in the literature. PCR products were checked on 1.2% agarose gel and subsequently sent for Sanger sequencing. The obtained sequences were compared through BLASTn and MycoBank for definitive identification. Each identified strain was preserved by cryopreservation at -80°C in sterile H_2O and by lyophilization, stored in sealed vials as long-term backup.

Growth experiment in darkness

To evaluate fungal growth on different paper substrates, four types of paper were used: Whatman No. 1 (normal and artificially aged) and Amalfi paper (normal and artificially aged). Standardized spore suspensions (5×10^6 spores/ $5 \mu\text{l}$) of *P. chrysogenum*, *C. cladosporioides*, and *A. niger* were prepared. The inoculated paper samples were incubated in darkness at 25°C for 4 weeks. Mycelial thickness was measured weekly using a metallographic microscope, while the colonized area was quantified using FIJI-ImageJ.

Experiment with light sources

Experimental boxes were constructed and equipped with four different light sources:

- cold white light (6226 K),
- warm white light (2435 K),
- monochromatic blue LED (426 nm),
- monochromatic red LED (631 nm).

Spectral irradiance was measured with a spectrophotometer to ensure uniform illumination.

Paper samples (Whatman No. 1) inoculated separately with *P. chrysogenum* and *C. cladosporioides* were exposed for 4 weeks. Mycelial growth was assessed by measuring hyphal thickness under a metallographic microscope and by image analysis; selected samples were prepared for SEM observation.

Experiment at different relative humidity ranges

To assess the influence of relative humidity, experimental boxes containing saturated salt solutions were prepared: $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (33%), K_2CO_3 (44%), and NaCl (75%). Growth of *P. chrysogenum* on Whatman No. 1 paper (normal and artificially aged) was monitored weekly by measuring mycelial thickness and analyzing digital images using FIJI.

2.3.4 Conclusions

The mycological collection established within the project represents a fundamental resource for documenting the fungal biodiversity associated primarily with paper-based cultural heritage materials, providing a stable reference system for the development of targeted experimental investigations. Growth tests conducted on different paper substrates confirmed that both the chemical composition and the degree of aging of the material significantly influence colonization patterns of the main fungal species, with *P. chrysogenum*, *C. cladosporioides*, and *A. niger* exhibiting substrate-specific preferences and distinct growth behaviors.

Controlled exposure to different illumination wavelengths demonstrated that light acts as a regulatory factor rather than a direct determinant of growth: cold white light markedly inhibited *P. chrysogenum*, whereas warm white and red light promoted the colonization capacity of *C. cladosporioides*. Similarly, relative humidity was confirmed as a crucial parameter for fungal activity: low values (33–44%) strongly limited growth, while higher values (75%) allowed measurable colonization, although still reduced compared to the control.

Overall, these results highlight the complexity and variability of fungal responses to environmental parameters, emphasizing that the risk of biodeterioration cannot be generalized but must be assessed in relation to the specific microclimatic conditions, substrate type, and fungal species involved. The knowledge acquired therefore contributes to refining preventive conservation strategies and supports the development of more effective environmental control measures for this category of cultural heritage materials.

Contribution to congress

Maria Francesca Sannino, Gemma T. Colesanti, Gabriele Capone, Antonino De Natale, Francesco Di Concilio, Antonino Pollio, "Assessing microbiological degradation of paper: a study of fungal contamination in Campania libraries". Congress "Patrimonio culturale al futuro: sostenibilità sociale, innovazione tecnologica, trasformazione digitale. Le ricerche in corso nel Progetto CHANGES". Roma 23-25 January 2025.

Laura Bellia and Maria Francesca Sannino, *"Tecniche radiometriche per la diagnosi e la ricerca di strategie volte alla limitazione di effetti fotobiologici"*. Congress "CATACOMBE E IPOGEI. Facciamo luce sul controllo dei potenziali biodeteriogeni in epoca di cambiamenti climatici". Catacombe di Domitilla, Roma, 28 May 2025.

Maria Francesca Sannino, Miriam Alberico, Francesca Diglio, Francesca Fragiasso, Alessandro Vergara, Laura Bellia, Boris Igor Palella, Giuseppe Riccio, Antonino Pollio, "Characterizing potential biodeteriogenic fungi from heritage contexts: experimental evaluations for sustainable conservation". Workshop "Sustainable Diagnostics and Cultural Heritage: Achievements and Perspectives of CHANGES Spoke 5". Catania 28-30 October 2025.

2.4 UNIFI (DST): Diagnostics and applications on paleobiological materials from deep time chronologies

2.4.1 Introduction

UNIFI (DST) involvement in WP4 concerns the creation of a new diagnostic and applications for the study of palaeobiological materials from deep time chronologies to investigate evolutionary patterns, functional morphology and other palaeoecological traits in fossil animals. WP 4 works on "organic materials in cultural heritage" and the Deliverables D4.2 object of the present document are "New digital, molecular, chemical/physical data archive for biological and palaeobiological materials". Why is the "Deep Time" specification mentioned for this specific Research Unit? The reason is simple and is based on the statements within 1970 UNESCO's Convention (U70) where the palaeontological heritage is included under the definition of "cultural heritage" [AM94; FBR23]. According to U70 (UNESCO Convention of the Means of Prohibiting the Illicit Import, Export, and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property), the term cultural heritage encompasses several main categories of heritage, such as "rare collections and specimens of fauna, flora, minerals, anatomy, and objects of palaeontological interest." On the other hand, the term "natural heritage" includes "natural sites with cultural aspects such as cultural landscapes and physical, biological, or geological formations" (U22) and since the fossil record is tightly connected and inseparable from the geological environment, it can be argued that fossil resources could be framed as part of the natural heritage because fossils are natural objects, not created by humans (P08).

Among the activities specified for WP4, we focus here on the activity "reconstructing information and providing technology and artistic knowledge for the conservation and enhancement of Cultural Heritage" using advanced methodologies for non-invasive diagnostics, and reconstruction of information useful for the conservation, enhancement and study of palaeobiological materials, namely A) retrodeformation procedures, and B) palaeobiological reconstruction for biomechanic inferences.

A) Retrodeformation procedures

Several taphonomic processes are known to alter the physical preservation of fossil remains. Therefore, fossils usually become badly deformed (e.g., losing biological symmetry, being compressed or bent) or incomplete [S81; L94; SPDM18]. The lack of this valuable information worsens the already fragmentary fossil record, which limits the opportunity to study fossil remains with the same analytical power that is typical for neontological samples. Therefore, palaeontologists must face the classic challenge to take the best out of specimens which show significant deformations, miss anatomical parts, or both.

B) Paleobiological reconstruction for biomechanic inferences.

Despite their ecological impact as predators, several aspects concerning canid palaeoecology remain poorly investigated. This is curious because their evolutionary history displays an intriguing variability in feeding-related adaptations, representing an attractive research topic. Considering the present diversity of canids, the palaeoecological investigation at the base of the modern clades appears an insightful task to reconstruct the past of this important carnivore family. To unravel this matter, several studies explored the morphology of teeth and snout of extant and fossil canids, even the inner features of the cranium can provide useful clues about the palaeoecology and evolution of extinct forms and some authors investigated the role and function of the respiratory turbinates in canids and felids, and others performed comparative morphological and quantitative studies of the frontal sinuses across the family Canidae. Since the morphofunctional aspects of the skull can be crucial to understand the way of living of the more basal and enigmatic species in the last decade, the use of digital biomechanical analysis has become a widespread approach to simulate biological structures and investigate mechanical performance of extinct taxa. Among the several methods employed in computed biomechanics (e.g., multibody dynamics, computed fluid dynamics), the finite element analysis (FEA) appears as one of the most robust thanks to its flexibility and the multiple type of data provided, such as (among others) stress, displacement and reaction forces [R07]. To explore this topic, we digitally simulated the bite of the medium-sized fossil canid *Eucyon davisii* (Late Miocene- Early Pliocene) and the Early to Middle Pleistocene wolf-like dogs *Canis borjigali* and *Canis mosbachensis* using FEA. The aim of these studies is the improvement of our knowledge on the feeding ecology of this basal and modern Canini through the comparison of its reaction stress and bite efficiency with those obtained from a sample of extant Canidae.

2.4.2 Methodology

A) Retrodeformation procedures

We have developed a new virtual reconstruction protocol, termed Target Deformation, which takes advantage of recent progress in digital restoration of fossil specimens, including retrodeformation [SPDM18], digital alignment of disarticulated portions [PBDM19], and 3D thin

plate spline transformation (tps3d) [SPDM18] to provide the virtual reconstruction of badly deformed, partially incomplete cranial material by using target fossil remains of the same species. We demonstrate here that our procedure is viable even by using very incomplete target remains, which are common in the fossil record and cannot be used by themselves in comparative analyses. The procedure is performed in R Environment v. 4.2.2 and it includes a combination of the digital techniques described in recent papers [SPDM18; CMSB20].

In the case of the retrodeformation of a cranium of the Early Pleistocene dog *Canis arnensis*, the workflow includes three consecutive steps, as follows:

1. Perform the retrodeformation of the *C. arnensis* cranium from Poggio Rosso IGF 7919V by using a bilateral landmark configuration to symmetrize the target specimen IGF 7919V_R.
2. Perform the retrodeformation of the *C. arnensis* lectotype, the cranium IGF 867, using a bilateral landmark configuration to restore the symmetry of the lectotype, IGF 867_R.
3. Warp the retrodeformed lectotype onto the retrodeformed IGF 7919V_R to obtain the final TD (Target Deformation) mesh of the *C. arnensis* lectotype, IGF 867_W.

All 3D meshes in this workflow have been standardized to 500.000 triangles to be more versatile in R. Moreover, we sampled only landmarks and not semi-landmarks due to the irregularity of the surfaces of the specimens considered in the analyses, e.g., due to cracks and fragile deformations of the crania. The landmark configurations were manually sampled on Amira software (ver. 5.4.5; www.thermofisher.com/amira-avizo).

The two retrodeformations undertaken on the original crania IGF 7919V and IGF 867 were performed with the function "retroDeformMesh()" embedded in the Morpho R package [S17].

The "retroDeformMesh()" algorithm was implemented by SPDM18 and it computes a non-linear symmetrisation detecting multiple local affine deformations and reducing the interpolation performed by thin-plate spline, TPS50. This function uses a set of bilateral landmarks for which their centroid is computed for each pair of landmarks.

We performed retrodeformation of the IGF 7919V 3D mesh, with a set of 112 bilateral landmarks (Figure 8, Step a) that defines the complete morphology of the cranium. As reported above, the aim of this retrodeformation is to restore the original symmetry of IGF 7919V. This process aims to remove asymmetric alterations due to taphonomic processes which affected the target specimen. At the end of this first process, we obtained IGF 7919V_R, the completely symmetrized 3D mesh of the Poggio Rosso cranium.

With the same procedure, we performed the retrodeformation on IGF 867 with an expanded set of 156 bilateral landmarks, to restore its original symmetry, with the larger set of landmarks possible because of better preservation (Figure 8, Step b). At the end of this process, we obtained IGF 867_R, the symmetrized 3D mesh of the *C. arnensis* lectotype.

Finally, to undertake the Target Deformation for the lectotype IGF 867, we selected a new landmark configuration of 152 homologous landmarks (Figure 8, Step c) that could be identified on both IGF 867_R and IGF 7919V_R, and we warped IGF 867_R using the new IGF 7919V_R landmark set. The warping process was performed through R function "tps3d()" (included in the

package Morpho [S17]) which deforms a set of coordinates or a mesh via thin plate spline transformation based on a reference and a target configuration. This final step produced the retrodeformed and warped-to-target mesh of the *C. arnensis* lectotype, IGF 867_W. To compare results between the retrodeformed and warped 3D meshes relative to the original ones, we computed and visualize pairwise surface distances with the function meshDist ('Morpho' R package by S17) between IGF 7919V and IGF 7919V_R, and IGF 867, IGF 867_R and IGF 867_W. The differences between surfaces were computed as Euclidean distances between corresponding points of the surfaces.

Figure 8: comparison of the 3D models obtained with Target Deformation. (a) IGF 7919V; specimen used as target. (b) Result of symmetrisation process applied to the target before its use in the Target Deformation protocol. (c) IGF 867, type of cranium of *Canis arnensis* and lectotype of the species. (d) IGF 867_R from the preliminary symmetrisation of the lectotype. (e) IGF 867_W, the final target deformation model reconstruction. Colour gradient (from blue to red) indicates the increase in mesh vertex displacement in millimetres in IGF 7919V_R (B), IGF 867_R (D) and IGF 867_W (E). Specimens not to scale.

Then we applied the “show.asymmetry” algorithm [MPBC21], a landmark-based procedure which allows visualization and measurement of the left–right asymmetry of each specimen; asymmetry

equals the square root of the sum of the squared distances between each landmark pairs. By implementing show.asymmetry, the asymmetry pattern is automatically visualized on one half of the object surface. The complete set of data and scripts (including the R script, the original IGF 7919V and IGF 867 3D meshes and the landmark sets) to replicate this workflow is provided in at the following link: [https:// doi. org/ 10. 5281/zenodo. 10418 654](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418654).

B) Paleobiological reconstruction for biomechanic inferences.

In this case all the specimens were examined by medical CT-scan, and the image stacks were imported within the open-source software 3D Slicer 5.6.1 (<https://www.slicer.org/>) [FBKF12]. A first rough segmentation of the crania was obtained using threshold-based algorithms, which select the voxels within a density range. Subsequently, the segmentations were refined manually. Since we were interested in testing the mechanical behaviour of the cranium during a biting action, we did not include in the segmentations the turbinates and most of the cribriform plate. Indeed, these bones are thin and covered of soft tissue, consequently they should not greatly affect our mechanical results [TW20]. Moreover, to lighten our simulations and considering that these studies are focused on the cranium, we filled the cavities of the mandibles obtaining a so-called cavity-filling 3D mesh. Finally, the segmentations representing crania, dentitions and mandible were exported from 3D Slicer as separate .STL files. All the exported 3D models were remeshed using the “remesh” algorithm of Autodesk Meshmixer; this passage was aimed to improve their topology. The 3D meshes were imported within the open-source software Blender 4.2.1 (<https://www.blender.org/>) and the crania and mandibles were aligned setting a jaw gape angle of 45°. The damaged parts (e.g., postorbital processes and zygomatic arches) were reconstructed using the preserved portions of the specimens as reference (mirroring) as well as the morphology of strictly related canid taxa.

Biomechanical simulations on taxa having different size may be influenced by scaling effects and consequently led to biased conclusions [SDV09; DGS09]. To avoid this, we maintained the same input force/surface area ratio in all the simulations, scaling all the crania to the surface area of a reference specimen/taxon and using the muscle force estimated for this specimen/taxon. Notably, since we employed a linear Finite Element (FE) solver, any constant input force/surface area ratio could be applied [SDV09]. The force exerted by the masticatory muscles of canidae was estimated using the dry-skull method, thus multiplying the anatomical cross-section area of the muscle by the specific muscular tension [T91] following what previously did in many other papers investigating the mammalian bite.

The meshes of the crania, teeth and mandibles were exported as .STL files and loaded in Strand7 R3.1.5 (<https://www.strand7.com>, Strand7 Pty. Ltd., Sydney, Australia) for the creations of the solid mesh and the setting of the boundary conditions. After a cleaning of the 3D models, we used the tool “automesh from plates” to generate solid meshes made of 4-noded tetrahedral elements. The number of tetrahedral elements varied between 2,638,957 and 3,657,249 for the cranium, and between 523,174 and 3,189,790 for the dentition. Following previously published procedures, we assigned to the crania and teeth values of elastic modulus and Poisson’s ration that are typical

for mammalian bone ($E = 13.7$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$) and dentine ($E = 38.6$ GPa, $\nu = 0.4$). To simulate the temporo-mandibular joint, we placed two fixed constraints at level of the mandibular fossae allowing only the rotation around the axis perpendicular to the sagittal plane. Similarly, we placed two constrains on the mandible at the level of the mandibular condyles roughly in correspondence of those placed on the cranium. To bound the teeth to the cranium, we used a series of links both at the crown-root interface and the root apices (5 links on single-rooted teeth, 8 links on double-rooted teeth and 9 on triple-rooted teeth). These entities have the function of transmitting the displacement and/or rotation from one node to another. For the simulations performed, the following muscular groups were considered for the elevation of the mandible: the temporalis group, the masseter group and the pterygoid group. For the origins and attachment areas of the masticatory muscles, we based our work on the published material [H12]. The muscles were simulated in Strand7 using pretensioned beam elements transmitting an axial compression, defined as trusses. The tension was calculated dividing the muscle force estimated with the dry-skull method by the number of trusses assigned to the relative muscle group. The number of trusses for each cranial side was 104: 65 for the temporalis muscle, 27 for the masseter muscle and 12 for the pterygoid group. The contact with the food item was simulated through a fixed constraint placed on the tip of the teeth involved in the simulations. To expand the bite scenarios examined in this study, we performed diverse simulations varying the position of the constraints on teeth. Consequently, we simulated:

- bilateral canine bite, two constraints at the tips of the C;
- unilateral carnassial bite, one constraint at the paracone of the P4;
- unilateral molar bite, one constraint at the protocone of the M1.

For the postprocessing of the results, the cranial reaction to the solicitations was expressed as von Mises stress, a widely accepted combined measure of the major stresses affecting a body under ductile failure condition and particularly valid for cortical bones [TW20; DGS09]. The mechanical efficiency of the tested crania was assessed and discussed through the study of the von Mises stress values and distribution. The comparison between the von Mises stress patterns observed in studied fossil specimens and those of the extant species allowed us to speculate about the paleoecology of the fossil forms in relation to their morphological adaptations.

2.4.3 Results and Conclusions

A) Retrodeformation procedures

The enhanced retrodeformation performed by implementing the "TDmethodology" [CMSB20] on the lectotype of *C. arnensis* IGF 867 (Figure 8, c), using the cranium from Poggio Rosso IGF 7919V (Figure 8 a) as a target reference specimen, produced encouraging results. The choice of IGF 7919V as a target to guide the retrodeformation is necessary because of the absence of undeformed or non-damaged specimens of *C. arnensis*, as none other complete or partial cranial fragments of this species have yet been recovered.

This paucity of material did not permit accounting for the fractures and displaced right side of the nasomaxillary region of IGF 7919V, as is visible in the final TD model IGF 867_W (Figure 8). Nevertheless, this 3D TD model (IGF 867_W) has produced a well restored digital specimen of the *C. arnensis* lectotype, IGF 867, more closely representing the in vivo shape and morphology of this individual. The morphometric analyses support the validity of the obtained 3D model of the retrodeformed type (IGF 867_W). The TD reconstruction and its morphometric results helped clarify some of the known unknowns [sensu J12] on this unusual Early Pleistocene *Canis* species. The target deformation reconstruction method applied to the fossil *Canis arnensis* lectotype represents not only an advance in permitting quantitative morphometric analyses of this key specimen, as demonstrated in this study, but also significantly in its future potential to update or extract additional taxonomic characteristics that may have been obscured by the post-mortem deformation of the skull. Specifically, the phylogenetic uncertainties associated with this taxon in past analyses could be lessened by explicitly coding a phylogenetic matrix or identifying taxonomically diagnostic discrete characters from the TD retrodeformed model of the lectotype.

Published papers:

BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., CIRILLI O., MELCHIONNA M., RAI A P., TSENG J. Z., FLYNN J., ROOK L. (2024). Virtual reconstructions of *Canis arnensis* holotype (Canidae, Mammalia) from Upper Valdarno Basin (Italy, Early Pleistocene). *Scientific Reports*, 14: 8303. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-024-53073-5

Participation to conferences:

ROOK L. (2024). Diagnostica e applicazioni su materiali paleobiologici da cronologie del tempo profondo. Evento di presentazione dello SPOKE 5 "SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DIAGNOSTICS OF CULTURAL HERITAGE" (PE5 CHANGES del PNRR) e dei bandi a cascata, 20-21 Febbraio 2024, Napoli

FROSALI S., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., MADURELL-MALAPEIRA J., URCIUOLI A., ROOK L. (2024). Analysis of the frontal sinus of Early Pleistocene canids. XXIV Edition of the "Giornate di Paleontologia" Pisa, 5-7 June 2024.

ROOK L., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., PERI E. (2024) Diagnostica non invasiva e applicazioni avanzate per restauro conservazione, tutela e valorizzazione di materiali paleobiologici: il WP4 dello Spoke 5 (Science and Technologies for Diagnostics of Cultural Heritage) all'interno del progetto CHANGES (Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society). XXIV Edition of the "Giornate di Paleontologia" Pisa, 5-7 June 2024.

B) Paleobiological reconstruction for biomechanic inferences.

The von Mises stress distribution obtained from the bite simulations in the studied canid species

are reported in Figure 9 for the case study of the Late Miocene *Eucyon davisi* and in Figure 10 for the case study of Early and Middle Pleistocene *Canis borjgali* and *Canis mosbachensis*. The mechanical behaviour of a complex structure like the mammalian cranium is a wide and complicated research topic. Surely, besides to the inner structure, there are multiple factors that concur to determine the stress pattern experienced by the cranium of a predator during a biting action. As an example, even the elongation of the snout and the cranial proportion play an important role in the structural reaction to the bite-related stresses. This is evident in *Lupulella adusta*, which appears as the species with the most stressed cranium among those included here, but it is also the form with the slenderest snout and elongated cranium. Despite this, from the present studies, it is evident that in the tribe Canini the frontal sinuses perform a stress-relieving and redistribution function on the stress generated by a bite. Further bite simulations on other Canidae species, both extant and extinct, will shed new light on the matter and will improve our comprehension of the ecology and palaeoecology of this important family of terrestrial predators.

Figure 9: distribution map of von Mises stress (σ_M) with the values scaled by the F_i/A ratio of *Eucyon davisi*. (a, d, g, j, m, p) bite simulations at the canine teeth, (b, e, h, k, n, q) bite simulations at the carnassial tooth, (c, f, i, l, o, r) bite simulations at the M1 tooth. The crania are in anterolateral view and not to scale. Note that the dotted pattern on

the neurocrania is due to the punctiform force exerted by the trusses simulating the muscle fibres.

Figure 10: distribution map of von Mises stress (σ_{vM}) of *Canis borjgali*, *C. mosbachensis* and extant canids. (A-I) bite simulations at the canine teeth, (A'-I') bite simulations at the carnassial tooth, (A''-I'') bite simulations at the M1 tooth. The crania are in anterolateral view and not to scale. Note that the dotted pattern on the neurocrania is due to the punctiform force exerted by the trusses simulating the muscle fibres.

Published papers:

PERI E., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., TSENG J.Z., ROOK L. (2025). Biomechanical bite simulation in *Eucyon davisi* (Mammalia, Canidae) and comparison with extant Canids. *Scientific Reports*, 15: 25786. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-025-95939-2

PERI E., CORRIDORI A., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., ROOK L., LORDKIPANIDZE D. (in review). Bite mechanics within the wolf lineage: feeding capabilities in *Canis borjgali* and *C. mosbachensis* inferred by digital bite simulation. *Royal Society Open Science*

Participation to conferences:

PERI E., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., ROOK L. (2023). Non-invasive advanced methodologies for diagnostic, restoration, protection, prevention and safe studies of deep time paleobiological material. 4° Convegno nazionale del Centro di Eccellenza DTC Lazio in collaborazione con CHANGES - Tecnologie e patrimonio culturale: nuove competenze e professioni, Roma, 30 novembre 2023

ROOK L. (2024). Diagnostica e applicazioni su materiali paleobiologici da cronologie del tempo profondo. Evento di presentazione dello SPOKE 5 "SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR

SUSTAINABLE DIAGNOSTICS OF CULTURAL HERITAGE" (PE5 CHANGES del PNRR) e dei bandi a cascata, 20-21 Febbraio 2024, Napoli

PERI E., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., ROOK L. (2024). Of bites and dogs: preliminary bite simulations in a fossil Canidae and insights on its palaeoecology. XXIV Edition of the "Giornate di Paleontologia" Pisa, 5-7 June 2024.

ROOK L., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., PERI E. (2024) Diagnostica non invasiva e applicazioni avanzate per restauro conservazione, tutela e valorizzazione di materiali paleobiologici: il WP4 dello Spoke 5 (Science and Technologies for Diagnostics of Cultural Heritage) all'interno del progetto CHANGES (Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society). XXIV Edition of the "Giornate di Paleontologia" Pisa, 5-7 June 2024.

PERI E., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., ROOK L. (2025). Digital biomechanics for cultural heritage: bite simulations of the fossil canid *Eucyon davisi* and new insight on its palaeoecology through non-invasive technologies. Convegno del Partenariato Esteso CHANGES, 23-24 Gennaio 2025, Roma

PERI E., CORRIDORI A., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., ROOK L. (2025). Bite mechanics through the wolf lineage: the case studies of *Canis borjgali* and *Canis mosbachensis*. Paleodays 2025, XXV Edizione delle Giornate di Paleontologia, 4-6 Giugno 2025, Catania

ROOK L., PERI E., CORRIDORI A., BARTOLINI-LUCENTI S., LORDKIPANIDZE D. (2025). Bite mechanics within the wolf lineage: Feeding capabilities of *Canis borjgali* and *Canis mosbachensis* inferred by digital bite simulation. International Congress "Abesalom Vekua – 100years from birth", November 3-4, 2025, Tbilisi Georgia.

3. Conclusions

The strontium isotope analyses carried out by UNIBO significantly expanded the availability of baseline data and contributed to the development of new regional isoscapes in several understudied areas. By integrating archaeological, anthropological, and environmental information, the project enabled more robust reconstructions of human and animal mobility across diverse contexts. The inclusion of modern plant sampling proved essential for strengthening local baselines while preserving archaeological materials. The resulting datasets provide a valuable long-term resource for the scientific community, supporting future interdisciplinary research.

Thanks to UNINA's work and research a multi-technique analytical framework based on advance chromatography – mass spectrometric techniques, strengthen the identification of archaeological organic residues, offering deeper insights into ancient dietary and technological practices.

A minimally invasive MALDI-MSI method using trypsin-functionalized sheets shows strong potential for spatially resolved protein mapping in cultural-heritage materials while limiting

damage to artifacts. Although promising, challenges in peptide recovery, spatial fidelity, and matrix optimization remain, guiding future improvements in sampling, imaging, and data interpretation.

The activities carried out by UNINA also have significantly expanded the knowledge on fungal biodiversity associated with paper-based cultural heritage materials, strengthening the role of the MYCUF collection as a reference resource. Experimental results demonstrated that light and relative humidity act as key factors in modulating the growth and activity of the main biodeteriogenic fungi, with species-specific responses. Overall, the data confirm the importance of targeted control of microclimatic parameters for the prevention of biodeterioration. These findings provide a solid scientific basis for the development of future preventive conservation and environmental management strategies.

UNIFI (DST) has excellently demonstrated how advanced analytical tools based on non-invasive techniques (CT-scan; Surface scan) implemented by powerful methodologies of elaboration/visualization in virtual environments strengthen our knowledge and visualization of “deep time” palaeobiological record, offering deeper insights into palaeobiology of these ancient forms. The potential of non-invasive approaches and analytical methods is crucial when dealing with such rare and unique cultural heritage objects. The fast availability of more powerful technologies (in terms of data acquisition and data processing) represent a promising and challenging frontiers for such kind of studies.

References

- [ALC21] Argentino, C., Lugli, F., Cipriani, A., Panieri, G., Testing miniaturized extraction chromatography protocols for combined $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ and $\delta^{88/86}\text{Sr}$ analyses of pore water by MC-ICP-MS. *Limnol Oceanogr Methods*. 2021; 19: 431–440. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lom3.10435>
- [AM94] Alcalá, L., Morales, I., Towards a definition of the Spanish palaeontological heritage. In *Geological and landscape conservation*. O'halloran D., Creen D., Hartes M., Síanley M., Knill K., 1994. London: *Geological Society*: 57–61.
- [BCW20] Bataille, C. P., Crowley, B. E., Wooller, M. J., Bowen, G. J., Advances in global bioavailable strontium isoscapes. *Palaeogeogr. Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.*; 2020; 555, 109849. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109849>
- [B06] Bentley, R.A., Strontium isotopes from the earth to the archaeological skeleton: a review. *J. Archaeol. Method Theory*; 2006; 13, 135–187. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-006-9009-x>
- [BM19] Borrego, S., Molina, A., Fungal assessment on storerooms indoor environment in the National Museum of Fine Arts, Cuba. *Air quality, atmosphere & health*; 2019; 12.11: 1373-1385. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11869-019-00765-x>

- [BPM99] Burton, J. H., Price, T. D., and Middleton, W. D., Correlation of bone Ba/Ca and Sr/Ca due to biological purification of calcium. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 26, 609–616. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jasc.1998.0378>
- [CMSB20] Cirilli, O., Melchionna, A., Serio, C., Bernor, R. L., Bukhsianidze, M., Lordkipanidze, D., Rook, L., Profico, A., Raia, P., Target deformation of the *Equus stenonis* holotype skull: A virtual reconstruction. *Front. Earth Sci.* 2020; 8: 1–12.
- [CNRMGB18] Cicatiello, P., Ntasi, G., Rossi, M., Marino, G., Giardina, P., & Birolo, L., Minimally invasive and portable method for the identification of proteins in ancient paintings. *Anal Chem.*, 2018; 90, 10128–10133. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b01718>.
- [DBP22] Di Carlo, E., Barresi, G., Palla, F., Biodeterioration. In: *Biotechnology and conservation of cultural heritage*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022. p. 1–30. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-97585-2_1
- [DCBE20] Dunne, J., Chapman, A., Blinkhorn, A., Evershed, R.P., Fit for purpose? Organic residue analysis and vessel specialisation: The perfectly utilitarian medieval pottery assemblage from West Cotton, Raunds, *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 2020; 120, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2020.105178>
- [DGS09] Dumont, E. R., Grosse, I. R., Slater, G. J., Requirements for comparing the performance of finite element models of biological structures. *J. Theor. Biol.* 2009; 256: 96–103.
- [EGD01] Ehrlich, S., Gavrieli, I., Dor, L. B., & Halicz, L., Direct high-precision measurements of the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratio in natural water, carbonates and related materials by multiple collector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS). *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2001; 16(12), 1389–1392. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B107996B>
- [FBKF12] Fedorov, A., Beichel, K., Kalpathy-Cramer, J. Finet, J., Fillion-Robin, J.-C., Pujol, S., Bauer, C., Jennings, D., Fennessy, F., Sonkal, M., Buatti, J., Aylward, S., Miller, J. V., Pieper, S., Kikinis, R., 3D Slicer as an image computing platform for the Quantitative Imaging Network. *Magn. Res. Imag.* 2012; 30: 1323–1341.
- [FBR23] Faggi, A., Bartolini-Lucenti, S., Rook, L., Assessing relevance and vulnerability of paleontological sites: a new analytic operational procedure. *Frontiers in Earth Sciences (Geoscience and Society)* 2023; 11: 1163280.
- [H12] Hermanson, J. W., The Muscular System. IN Evans, H. E. (ed.). *Miller's Anatomy of the Dog*. Elsevier Health Sciences; 2012; 185–280.
- [HQB04] Hodell, D. A., Quinn, R. L., Brenner, M., and Kamenov, G., Spatial variation of strontium isotopes ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) in the Maya region: A tool for tracking ancient human migration. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 2004; 31, 585–601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2003.10.009>

- [HCD92] Horwitz, E. P., Chiarizia, R., Dietz, M. L., A novel strontium-selective extraction chromatographic resin. *Solvent Extr Ion Exch.* 1992; 10: 313–336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07366299208918107>
- [J12] Jackson, S. T., Representation of flora and vegetation in quaternary fossil assemblages: Known and unknown knowns and unknowns. *Quat. Sci. Rev.* 2012; 49: 1–15.
- [L94] Lyman, R. L., *Vertebrate Taphonomy*. 1994. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- [LWG20] Lugli F., Weber M., Giovanardi T., Arrighi S., Bortolini E., Figus C., Marciani G., Oxilia G., Romandini M., Silvestrini S., Jochum K.P., Benazzi S., Cipriani A., Fast offline data reduction of laser ablation MC-ICP-MS Sr isotope measurements via the interactive Excel-based spreadsheet 'SrDR'. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2020; 35, 852–862. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9JA00424F>
- [LCB22] Lugli, F., Cipriani, A., Bruno, L., Ronchetti, F., Cavazzuti, C., Benazzi, S., A strontium isoscape of Italy for provenance studies. *Chem. Geol.*, 2022; 587, 120624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2021.120624>
- [MDNBTCBLFAC20] Melchiorre, C., Dello Iorio, C., Ntasi, G., Birolo, L., Trojsi, G., Cennamo, P., Barone Lumaga, M.R., Fatigati, G., Amoresano, A., Carpentieri, A., A multidisciplinary assessment to investigate a XXII Dynasty wooden coffin, *Int. J. Conserv. Sci.* 2020; 11, 25–38. ISSN: 2067533X
- [MHB01] McArthur, J.M., Howarth, R.J., Bailey, T.R., Strontium Isotope Stratigraphy: LOWESS Version 3: Best Fit to the Marine Sr-Isotope Curve for 0–509 Ma and Accompanying Look-up Table for Deriving Numerical Age. *J. Geol.*, 2001; 109 (2):155–70. <https://doi.org/10.1086/319243>
- [MPBC21] Melchionna, M., Profico A., Buzi, C., Castiglione, S., Mondanaro, A., Del Bove, A., Sansalone, G., Piras, P., Raia P., A new integrated tool to calculate and map bilateral asymmetry on three-dimensional digital models. *Symmetry*; 2021; 13: 1644.
- [N12] Nanci, A., *Ten Cate's Oral Histology Development, Structure, and Function*. St Louis: Elsevier Health Sciences.
- [NKSCSCB21]. Ntasi, G., Kirby, D. P., Stanzione, I., Carpentieri, A., Somma, P., Cicatiello, P., Birolo, L., A versatile and user-friendly approach for the analysis of proteins in ancient and historical objects. *J. Proteom.*, 2021; 231, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprot.2020.104039>
- [PBB02] Price, T. D., Burton, J. H., and Bentley, R. A., The characterisation of biologically-available strontium isotope ratios for investigation of prehistoric migration. *Archaeometry*; 2002; 44, 117–135 <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-4754.00047>
- [PBDM19] Profico, A., Buzi, C., Davis, C., Melchionna, M., Veneziano, A., Raia, P., et al., A new tool for digital alignment in virtual anthropology. *Anat. Rec.*, 2019; 302: 1104–1115. doi: 10.1002/ar.24077
- [PSM19] Pinheiro, A. C., Sequeira, S. O., Macedo, M. F., Fungi in archives, libraries, and museums: a review on paper conservation and human health. *Critical reviews in microbiology*, 2019, 45.5–6: 686–700. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1040841X.2019.1690420>

- [R07]: Rayfield, E. J., Finite element analysis and Understanding the biomechanics and evolution of living and fossil organisms. *Ann. Rev. Earth Pl Sc.* 2007; 35: 541–576.
- [S17] Schlager, S., Morpho and Rvcg—Shape analysis in R. In “Statistical Shape and Deformation Analysis”. Elsevier (2017): 217–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-810493-4.00011-0>.
- [S81]: Shipman, P., Life History of a Fossil and Introduction to Taphonomy and Paleoecology. Cambridge: Harvard University Press (1981).
- [SCM14] Sequeira, S. O., Cabrita, E. J.; Macedo, M. F., Fungal biodeterioration of paper: how are paper and book conservators dealing with it? An international survey. *Restaurator. International Journal for the Preservation of Library and Archival Material*, 2014, 35.2: 181-199. <https://doi.org/10.1515/rest-2014-0005>
- [SDV09] Slater, G. J., Dumont, E. R., Van Valkenburgh, B., Implications of predatory specialization for cranial form and function in canids. *J. Zool.* 2009; 278: 181–188
- [SGL25] Scaggion, C., Giovanardi, T., Loponte, D., Carbonera, M., Armaroli, E., Bernardin, i S., et al., Random forest-based bioavailable strontium isoscape for environmental and archaeological applications in central eastern Argentina and western Uruguay. *PLoS One*; 2025; 20(7): e0326047. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0326047>
- [SPDM18] Schlager, S., Profico, A., Di Vincenzo, F., Manzi, G., Retrodeformation of fossil specimens based in 3D bilateral semi-landmarks: implementation in the R package “Morpho”. *PLoS One*; 2018; 13: e0194073. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0194073
- [T91] Thomason, J. J., Cranial strength in relation to estimated biting forces in some mammals. *Canad. J. Zool.* 1991; 69: 2326–2333
- [TW20] Tseng, Z. J., Wang X., Cranial functional morphology of fossil dogs and adaptation for durophagy in *Borophagus* and *Epicyon* (Carnivora, Mammalia). *J. Morph.* 2010; 271: 1386–1398
- [VDCPNB16] Vinciguerra. R., De Chiaro. A., Pucci. P., Marino. G., Birolo L., Proteomic strategies for cultural heritage: From bones to paintings, *Microchem. J.*, 2016; 126, 341–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2015.12.024>.